

PARACHOR OF MOLECULAR IODINE AND OF POTASSIUM IODIDE IN WATER

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By W. V. BHAGWAT AND S. O. SHUKLA

The parachor of molecular iodine is about 192 as determined in ethyl alcohol and benzene. The value is more than double for atomic iodine (91). The variation is similar to that in the case of Br_2 , Cl_2 , H_2 , etc. Parachor of KI in water varies from 150-156 for molar fractions of KI ranging from 0.0325 to 0.0989.

The parachor of atomic iodine is determined by Sugden (Sugden, "Parachor and Valency", p. 180) by the study of organic compounds of the elements. The value is 91.0. However, the value in solution is not known. This must correspond to the parachor of molecular iodine. The values in ethyl alcohol and benzene are given below. x stands for the molar fraction of iodine and $1-x$ for molar fraction of the solvent.

TABLE I

x .	$1-x$.	M_m .	Temp.	D .	γ .	P_m .	P_x .
Parachor of molecular iodine (I_2) is ethyl alcohol.							
0.0185	0.9815	50.01	25°	0.8539	22.8	127.9	193.7
0.0328	0.9672	52.85	25°	0.9024	23.45	128.8	190.9
0.0408	0.9591	54.51	25°	0.9320	23.68	129.0	189.9
Parachor of I_2 in benzene (parachor of benzene = 206.5).							
0.0182	0.9818	80.75	25°	0.9170	30.14	206.14	196.2

The results indicate that the value of molecular iodine, I_2 , is near about 192. This is more than twice the value for atomic parachor of iodine (91). Iodine molecule has covalent link and Sugden assumes that single covalent link does not contribute towards parachor and the value for molecular iodine I-I should be $2 \times 91 = 182$. However, the result is not surprising since this deviation between the values of atomic and molecular parachor seems to be common, as will be illustrated by the following results in Table II (*vide* Sugden, "Parachor and Valency", p. 187).

TABLE II

Atomic parachor	Molecular parachor
Obs.	Calc. from atomic parachor
Br = 68	Br—Br = 132.1
Cl = 54.3	Cl—Cl = 111.5; 104.6
H = 17.1	H—H = 35.2
N = 12.5	N=N = 60.4
O = 20	O=O = 54.2

A double bond contributes by 23.2 and a triple bond by 46.6 towards parachor. Hence parachor of N_2 should be 71.6 and of O_2 , 63.2. It is clear therefore that there are other factors which govern the parachor in molecular state than the simple relation. The value of 192 for I_2 is therefore not at all surprising.

Jager (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, 101, 1) has determined the surface tension of fused potassium iodide at several temperatures between 737° and 812°. These values have been utilised by

Sudgen (*loc. cit.*, p. 178) to determine its parachor. The values range between 204.3 and 206.9 and the value 205.2 is taken as a mean. From the values of parachors of fused potassium salts the value of atomic parachors of potassium comes out to be 110. Actually the value fluctuated from 84 to 115. Similar work with sodium salts give $P_{Na}=80$. Actual determination of parachor of sodium by fusing it, gives a value 97.4 (Pointdexter, *Physical Rev.*, 1926, 27, ii, 820). This suggests that value of P_K as obtained by Sudgen may not be reliable.

Ray's work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 46) on potassium iodide in aqueous solution gives a value 103.1-145.2 for molar fraction of KI = 0.11 to 0.086. These values are very different from that of fused salt. Ray's results are for one definite temperature and the values of surface tension are neither gradually increasing or decreasing. In spite of this the value of parachor steadily increases with the increase of molar fraction. The results need revision. Our results are as follows.

TABLE III

Parachor of potassium iodide in water (Parachor of $H_2O=52.44$)

x	$1-x$	M_m	Temp.	D	γ	P_m	P_x
0.0325	0.9675	22.85	25°	1.2044	74.66	55.63	150.8
"	"	"	30°	1.201	72.26	55.67	152.0
0.0491	0.9509	25.27	25°	1.296	75.51	57.45	154.64
0.0789	0.9211	29.69	25°	1.454	77.14	60.5	154.6
"	"	"	30°	1.449	75.2	60.29	151.95
"	"	"	40°	1.442	72.92	60.16	150.3
0.0989	0.9011	32.64	25°	1.552	79.29	62.74	156.6
"	"	"	30°	1.546	77.41	62.64	155.5
"	"	"	40°	1.539	75.37	62.5	154.1
"	"	"	50°	1.530	72.85	62.34	152.5

The deviation observed in case of Ray's results may be due to the fact that the molar range investigated by him is large while the mixture law gives consistent results provided molar fractions of the solute and solvent do not differ widely.